

Brazilian Community Report on Neutrino Physics

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Abstract

This white paper describes the main activities of the Brazilian groups in the neutrino program based at Fermilab. The main efforts are being expended in the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) and in the Short Baseline Neutrino Detector (SBND). The Brazilian groups are having a major role in several areas of these experiments. The Photon Detection System of the DUNE far detector will be based on a device, the X-ARAPUCA, conceived and developed in Brazil and a significant number of X-ARAPUCAs will be installed in the SBND detector. Major contributions are also being given in the development of Monte Carlo simulations of both SBND and DUNE detectors. Several Brazilian groups are also involved with leading roles in the working groups which are investigating the prospects of the DUNE experiment for Beyond Standard Model Physics and for Supernova neutrino Physics.

1 Introduction

The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) is one of the most ambitious project in the actual experimental particle physics scenario. The far detector of the experiment will be constituted by a liquid argon time projection chamber with an active mass of 40 kton. The light detection system is a fundamental part of the detector and is used for triggering, time zero, particle identification and calorimetric purposes. At the moment the baseline option for the photon detection system of the DUNE far detector is based on the ARAPUCA concept. This is a light trap, which will allow to increase significantly the light detection efficiency of the detector with respect to the previous design based on scintillating/guiding bars.

2 DUNE

DUNE is aimed to address some of the open questions in neutrino physics, namely the measurement of the CP violating phase in the leptonic sector, the hierarchy of neutrino masses and the θ_{23} octant. The observation of CP violating effects would have a significant impact on the explanation of the matter/antimatter asymmetry of the Universe. Resolving the mass hierarchy would have significant cosmological, theoretical and experimental implications. It would drive, for instance, the design of future experiments aimed to discriminate between the hypotheses of Majorana or Dirac neutrino.

The Collaboration will make use of the most intense neutrino beam ever operated, which will originate from the Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory (Chicago, US), propagate for about 1,300 km to be detected by the far detector installed in the Sanford Underground Research Facility (SURF). The far detector will adopt the experimental technique of the Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPC) and will have a total active mass of 40,000 tons of liquid argon (LAr) segmented into four modules of 10,00 tons each.

The huge active mass of the far detector will also allow for a rich program

of non-beam physics, with particular emphasis on the possible detection of the neutrinos emitted in the explosion of a supernova and on the observation of the decay of the proton.

DUNE's observation of thousands of neutrinos from a core-collapse supernova (SNB - Supernova Burst) in the Milky Way would allow to peer inside a newly-formed neutron star and potentially witness the birth of a black hole.

Current theories beyond the Standard Model suggest that the three fundamental physical forces which are observed today were unified at the beginning of the Universe. Grand Unified Theories (GUTs) predict that protons should decay and DUNE will search for proton decay in the range of proton lifetimes predicted by a wide range of GUT models [1, 2, 3]

The proton decay was not observed yet and its detection would represent a major achievement in particle physics.

The detection of liquid argon scintillation light is an important part of the LArTPC technique since it is used for timing, triggering and calorimetric purposes.

LAr is an abundant scintillator and emits about 40 photons/keV when excited by minimum ionizing particle [4] in the absence of external Electric Fields.

The passage of ionizing radiation in LAr produces excitations and ionization of the argon atoms that ultimately result in the formation of the excited dimer Ar_2^* . Photon emission proceeds through the de-excitation of the lowest lying singlet and triplet excited states, $^1\Sigma$ and $^3\Sigma$, to the dissociative ground state. The de-excitation from the $^1\Sigma$ state is very fast and has a characteristic time of the order of $\tau_{fast} \simeq 6$ ns. The de-excitation from the $^3\Sigma$, state is much slower since it is forbidden by the selection rules; it has a characteristic time of $\tau_{slow} \simeq 1.5 \mu\text{sec}$. In both decays, photons are emitted in a 10 nm band centered around 127 nm, which is in the Vacuum Ultra-Violet (VUV) region of the electromagnetic spectrum [4]. This complicates their detection since the majority of cryogenic photo-sensor have acceptance windows which are not transparent to these wavelengths. A common strategy consists in down-converting the wavelength of scintillation photons to the visible with the use of organic wavelength-shifting (WLS) compounds which absorbs VUV light and re-emit it at longer wavelengths.

The relative intensity of the fast versus the slow component is related to the ionization density of LAr and depends on the ionizing particle: 0.3 for electrons, 1.3 for alpha particles and 3 for neutrons [5]. This phenomenon is the basis for the particle discrimination capabilities of LAr.

2.1 DUNE Photon Detection System

The DUNE far detector consists of detector systems for charge and light produced by an ionization event in the LArTPC. The charge detection system permits both calorimetry and position determination, with two of the three spatial coordinates (y and z) established by the position of the wires receiving the charge and the third (x) by the arrival time of the charge. Locating the x position requires an independent determination of the time of the ionization event, a clock start time. Two systems

provide this in DUNE: the Fermilab accelerator system for neutrino beam related events and the Photon Detection System (PDS).

Neutrino CP violation and other elements of the DUNE long-baseline neutrino program are possible without data from the PDS. The neutrino beam timing allows full functionality of the wire planes, and the deep underground location reduces the possibility of in-time background events from cosmic rays and other sources to a negligible level. Similarly, DUNE can detect SNB originating within the galaxy without the PDS since the presence of thousands of low-energy neutrino events, even if they consist only of few millimeter long tracks, provides an unambiguous signal in the TPC. By contrast, DUNE's nucleon decay physics could not be executed without the PDS. The inability to establish a clock start time (T_0) would make it impossible to determine whether a candidate proton decay event was fully contained in the detector volume or associated with objects entering the detector from the outside. Determining T_0 will also allow the energy reconstructed by the TPC to be corrected for charge lost due to electron capture and other transport effects in the TPC.

While only absolutely required for proton decay searches, the PDS directly enhances physics capabilities for all DUNE physics drivers, opens up prospects for further physics explorations, and contributes to a more robust set of operating points of the detector that help all physics. For SNB neutrino events, the PDS allows for proper location of the event vertex, and improves energy resolution by allowing for position-dependent energy corrections and complimentary direct calorimetric measurements, improving energy resolution and possibly greater sensitivity to underlying supernova dynamical models. The PDS also enables a complementary triggering scheme for the burst itself, increasing reliability, reducing dead time, and extending the sensitivity further out to nearby dwarf galaxies.

The PDS can also be used to directly measure energy calorimetrically for all classes of events, working as a cross-check to the energy measured by the TPC or improving the resolution when both measurements are used together. In the event that the DUNE TPC could not operate at its goal electric field of 500 V/cm, the PDS energy measurements could compensate for lessened charge detector performance because light production increases relative to that of free charge for lower electric fields.

The PDS could open new areas of investigation. The few-MeV scale solar neutrino interactions occur as isolated events in time and space. Suppression of radiological and noise related backgrounds to pull out a signal for these events likely requires redundant measurements with charge and light. The PDS may also provide a means for identifying events with Michel electrons produced from the decay of a stopped muon. Tagging these electrons can be used to estimate the anti-neutrino content of the beam flux or further reduce nucleon decay backgrounds.

The PDS is installed in the dead regions between different wire planes of the LArTPC and for this reason it needs to satisfy severe mechanical and technical constraints. In particular, the PDS modules need to be shaped in form of bars with a maximum thickness of 2 cm and planar dimensions of 200 cm \times 10 cm (l \times w).

Within these constraints, the PDS modules need to have a total detection efficiency at the level of few percent in order to meet the physics requirements of the DUNE experiment and be reasonably cheap in order to be produced on a large scale to be installed in the far detector.

The X-ARAPUCA currently represents the baseline choice for the photon detection system of the DUNE experiment.

The X-ARAPUCA is a development of the traditional ARAPUCA. This concept was conceived to reduce losses on the internal surfaces of the ARAPUCA by diminishing the average number of reflections before detection. The idea is to introduce a light-guide plate in the reflective cavity of a standard ARAPUCA parallel to the filter and with its same dimensions. A dichroic filter with a WLS deposited on its external side to convert the 127 nm photons to longer wavelengths (below the filter cutoff) is the window of the device. Converted photons traverse the filter and before reaching one of the inner surfaces of the box find an acrylic plate which acts as WLS and as a light guide. In fact, the acrylic plate has a WLS compound embedded inside it which converts the photon to a wavelength above the filter cutoff. The new configuration of the X-ARAPUCA allows for two different detection mechanisms:

- the photon when entering the X-ARAPUCA is converted by the WLS deposited on the filter and again converted by the WLS inside the acrylic plate, but it is not guided by the plate itself. In this case the photon can be reflected by the internal walls of the X-ARAPUCA until being detected by the SiPMs installed at one end of the box, exactly in the same way of a traditional ARAPUCA;
- the photon is converted by the filter and again converted by the WLS inside the plate, the photon can be guided inside the plate by total internal reflection if it is emitted with an angle greater than the critical angle of the interface acrylic/LAr. The photon will propagate up to the boundaries of the sheet where it is eventually detected by the array of SiPMs. This mechanism represents the main improvement with respect to a traditional ARAPUCA.

The net result is that the mean number of reflections of the photons on the internal surfaces of the X-ARAPUCA is substantially reduced with respect to a traditional ARAPUCA and consequently the collection efficiency is higher. The technology needed to convert the ARAPUCA design into the X-ARAPUCA one is quite well understood and mastered. The main modification consists in the introduction of the acrylic WLS plate inside the reflective cavity. WLS plates have been widely used inside the DUNE Collaboration in the recent past and have been demonstrated to be fully compatible with LAr temperature. Furthermore, they are available on the market at a reasonably low cost (hundreds dollars per square meter).

Preliminary studies using a Monte Carlo simulation provided quite encouraging results. The trapping efficiency of the photons inside an X-ARAPUCA is up to

50% higher than that of a traditional ARAPUCA [6].

The X-ARAPUCA represents the most relevant commitment in hardware of the Brazilian and Latin American groups in the DUNE experiment and it is a major contribution, since the PDS is one of the most important subsystems of the experiment.

3 protoDUNE

ProtoDUNE is the large scale prototype of the DUNE far detector, with an active mass around 1,000 tons of LAr. The detector construction was completed in the first half of 2018 and the detector was filled with LAr in October of the same year. The protoDUNE serves as a one to one test of all the subsystems which will be installed in the DUNE far detector. The PDS of protoDUNE consisted of three different technologies: the ARAPUCA and two different flavors of light-guide bars. The protoDUNE ARAPUCA system is constituted by two arrays of 16 standard ARAPUCAs. One of the arrays is shown in figure 1.

The ARAPUCA arrays have shown to have an efficiency several times higher with respect to the other two technologies.

The X-ARAPUCA represents a further improvement of the ARAPUCA technology and calls for a significant increase in efficiency and for a substantial simplification of the design. **These reasons led the PD Consortium to propose the X-ARAPUCA as the baseline device for the PDS of the DUNE far detector.** The change from a traditional ARAPUCA to the X-ARAPUCA will require a dedicate test in protoDUNE. This will happen during the second run of the detector, which will start at the beginning of 2022. Thirty modules of X-ARAPUCAs arrays will be assembled, tested, qualified at the Lboratorio de Leptons and installed in the detector at CERN. This represents a significant effort of the Brazilian Community working in the ARAPUCA project and is a consistent fraction of the present project.

4 SBND

4.1 SBN program

Experimental observations of neutrino oscillations have established a picture consistent with the mixing of three neutrino flavors (ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ) with three mass eigenstates (ν_1, ν_2, ν_3) whose differences turn out to be relatively small, with $\Delta m_{31}^2 = 2.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$ and $\Delta m_{21}^2 = 7.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$. However, in recent years, several experimental “anomalies” have been reported which, if experimentally confirmed, could be hinting at the presence of additional neutrino states with larger mass-squared differences participating in the mixing

Figure 1: One of the ARAPUCA arrays is protoDUNE is the segmented withish bar behind the wire planes. The other, unsegmented modules are light-guide bars.

Two distinct classes of anomalies pointing at additional physics beyond the Standard Model in the neutrino sector have been reported, namely a) the apparent disappearance signal in low energy anti-neutrinos from nuclear reactors beyond the expected θ_{13} effect (the "reactor anomaly") and from Mega-Curie radioactive neutrino sources in the Gallium experiments originally designed to detect solar neutrinos (the "Gallium anomaly") b) the evidence for an electron-like excess in interactions coming from neutrinos from particle accelerators (the "LSND and Mini-BooNE anomalies") [3].

None of these results can be described by oscillations between the three Standard Model neutrinos and, therefore, could be suggesting important new physics with the possible existence of at least one fourth non-standard neutrino state, driving neutrino oscillations at a small distance, with typically $\Delta m^2 \sim 0.1 \text{ eV}^2$.

Considering the present experimental scenario, an accelerator-based neutrino beam facility provides the best opportunity for a rich oscillation research program with a single experiment, where the existence of an oscillation signal in ν_e appearance and disappearance modes as well as ν_μ disappearance can be simultaneously investigated. Neutrino or anti-neutrino beams can be produced in the same experiment and, at accelerator beam energies, both charged current and neutral-current channels can be explored. This is the approach of the short-baseline neutrino oscillation program on the FNAL Booster Neutrino Beam.

The short-baseline neutrino program (SBN) [7] is proposed to include three Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber detectors (SBND-MicroBooNE-ICARUS) located on-axis in the Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB) at FERMILAB. The near

detector SBND will be located enclosure 110 m from the BNB target, the Micro-BooNE detector, at 470 m and ICARUS T600 will be located 600 m from the target

4.2 R&D for DUNE

Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber detectors are quickly becoming the state of the art in neutrino detectors. The currently long-baseline neutrino experiment, DUNE, will be using liquid argon technology. In the framework of the US-based neutrino programme, in a relatively short time, these detectors have had to evolve from small chambers like LArIAT to mid-size chamber like MicroBooNE and SBND to extremely large-scale projects like DUNE.

This has necessitated a focus on development of engineering solutions for these larger scale detectors leaving somewhat less resources to improve the technology itself.

One area that has not been fully exploited is the collection of scintillation light emitted by the argon. LArTPCs at neutrino energies are focused on charge collection with wire planes and have mostly used scintillation light **for triggering only**.

Scintillation light can be used to enhance the performance of liquid argon detectors in neutrino physics in several ways: the most obvious ones being energy reconstruction, timing, position reconstruction and triggering.

One of the goals of the Short-Baseline Near Detector (SBND) is to develop the liquid argon technology in addition to its rich physics programme. From the beginning, one of the main areas of this R&D has been scintillation light, and one of the options has been installing new solutions for the photon detector. The aim of this potential new detector element was to develop light collection technology for future large scale detectors.

4.3 The photon detector of SBND

The SBND experiment also hosts a LArTPC although much smaller in size with respect to the DUNE one. It has an interesting photon detection system in which different technologies can be compared. The SBND TPC anodic plane is segmented into four parts called Anode Plane Assemblies (APAs). The photon detection system will be mounted on the 4 APAs with 6 mounting frames. Each mounting frame has space for the installation of the photon detectors.

The primary photon detection system of the experiment is based on traditional 8-inch diameter photomultiplier (PMT). Six PMTs will be installed in each mounting frame. Five of them will observe the active volume of the detector while 1 will be positioned in the opposite direction to be used as a veto. As this experiment has enough space to host new photon detection devices for R&D aimed at improving the final design of the DUNE PDS, 196 X-ARAPUCAs will also be installed in SBND. The photon detection system Box is illustrated in **Fig. 2**.

Figure 2: SBND Photon Detection System Box. PMTs and ARAPUCAS sharing the same PD BOX

4.4 ARAPUCA system

The ARAPUCA concept has been proposed as a simple and neat solution for increasing the effective collection area of SiPMs through the shifting and trapping of scintillation light in noble liquids. It has great potential of improving timing and calorimetry resolution in neutrino and dark matter search experiments using time projection chambers with an expected single photon detection efficiency larger than 1%. The initial design consists of a box made of highly reflective internal surface material and with an acceptance window for photons composed of two shifters and a dichroic filter.

The ARAPUCA system in SBND is divided in two different readout electronics named APSAIA and Daphne. The APSAIA will readout 32 channels from ARAPUCAs and X-ARAPUCAs and the Daphne electronics will readout 192 readout channels. The APSAIA system will use a $6 \times 6 \text{mm}^2$ SiPM while the Daphne will readout a $3 \times 3 \text{mm}^2$ SiPM.

The ARAPUCA system do not represent only an RD for DUNE but can provide some important information for the physics, as well as:

- Discriminating between visible and near-ultraviolet light, noting that the lightbars are sensitive to VUV light only.
- Two dimensional tracking, improved ash-matching, increased photocoverage, and enhanced granularity.
- Rejection of beam-external TPC events, noting that the lightbars can "light from either side of each bar.

Final considerations

The SBND detector is the unique opportunity to test new versions of ARAPUCA and the X-ARAPUCA device for the first time, furthermore in a real LArTPC experiment. The timeline for the installation of the system is at the end of March 2019. All of devices will be produced entirely in Brazil. This represents an opportunity not only for testing these new devices but also to prove that we are able to develop and produce instrumentation of high level and low cost in our country.

5 Software Development

One important tool used to predict the consequences of changing parameters in the ARAPUCA design was the development of a complete Monte Carlo simulation of the device using the Geant4 framework [9, 10]. Studies included the dependence of the efficiency as a function of the number and positioning of SiPMs, the device's geometry, changes in the shifters properties, and properties of the dichroic filter. More information can be found in references [11, 6]. This work has helped in the design choices made for the ARAPUCAs to be installed in SBND and DUNE.

The development of reconstruction methods for using the light in physics analysis with Monte Carlo simulations is also a key factor within the experiments themselves. For DUNE and SBND, as well as other LArTPC experiments, the LArSoft framework, a platform that brings together a number of adequate softwares for simulation, reconstruction, and analysis of events in liquid argon TPCs, is used. The specific software for the different collaborations are built over this platform and include particular characteristics, such as the detector geometry, particle-matter interactions and electronic responses.

The Brazilian group has been involved in improving the collaboration software for better description of light production and propagation in Monte Carlo simulations, generate its electronic readout signal and properly analyse it. This includes a more trustworthy description of the geometry of the PDS and the tools used for generating light from the energy deposition of charged particles up to its arrival at the sensors and the development of analysis tools for physical interpretation. With these developments, it will be possible to evaluate and refine predictions for the PDS in terms of the temporal distribution of the arrival of photons in the detector, temporal and spatial resolution and calorimetry.

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